

An Automatic Glass Burette Jet.

By D. R. PARANJPE AND D. V. CHANDERKAR.

The burettes used in Intermediate Chemistry laboratories are usually cheap ones without ground glass stoppered jets. In ordinary practice they are provided with a separate jet connected with the drawn out end of the burette and the flow is controlled by a pinch-cock. These pinch-cocks are easily spoilt and cause a permanent stricture in the connecting rubber tube.

The automatic jet, described here, does away with the pinch-cock. It may be used also on the delivery tubes of Kipp's H_2S generators, thus stopping much wastage of the material when the generator cock is inadvertently left open. The jet is extremely simple to make and has replaced the pinch-cock in this laboratory.

FIG. 1. FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

To make an automatic jet, an ordinary jet is first drawn as at D (Figs. 1 and 2). The tube is then closed at A and a small circular

opening made at B as shown. A slight drawing out of the tube as shown at C will be found useful.

To work the jet, a tight fitting rubber tube is slipped on up to the constriction C, where it can be tied on with a piece of thread, so as to cover the circular hole B.

No liquid will flow out when the burette is filled and the circular hole on the jet covered with rubber tubing as shown in Fig 3. To release the liquid, the rubber tubing is pinched at a spot immediately above the circular hole B (Fig. 2). When the rubber tube is lifted up in this way, the liquid from the burette enters the hole B and escapes through the jet. The flow can be easily controlled by pressing on the rubber tube connection, and with little practice even control over drops can be attained.

While using the jet it is very important that it should be freed from air-bubbles, otherwise titration errors will occur. To get rid of the air bubbles the flow is to be started as explained above and the jet turned from position (I) to position (II) as shown in Fig. 3.

If alkalis are used in the burette, there is danger of the rubber connection becoming slippery and so moving its position, thus causing a wrong reading. This is corrected by tying a piece of thread on the part D (Fig. 1) and fixing it there permanently.